

A New Approach to Unification: The Living Universe Hypothesis*

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As a result of searches for sources order, we have found several blockages to unification. Firstly the assumption that general relativity is complete; secondly that life is random in origin; thirdly that the hidden sector produces simple interactions at high energies, whereas it produces complex ordered states at ultra-low energies; and fourthly that the Universe is dead and lifeless. The first part of this paper contains an overview of four physics papers and one biophysics paper. The first physics paper introduces an extended version of general relativity (using chronometric invariants) which is combined with quantum mechanics to predict the photo-mirror hypothesis, namely that visible light can switch the direction of time into that of mirror space-time. The second paper presents experiments with light shining on water, which confirms the photo-mirror effect, and hence is evidence for unification. This also supports the evidence for magnetic monopoles at very low energies. The third paper presents evidence for a new type of radiation in sunlight in mirror space-time. The fourth presents evidence for quarks and preons in mirror space-time. The biophysics paper is a search for the origins of order in living organisms. The second part of the present paper is a higher level synthesis of these five papers. We find evidence for unification, and for the hidden sector of a potential new unified theory based upon quantum mechanics and chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR), which creates order out of chaos. We deduce that the complexity of life is physical in origin. We make the hypothesis that life is a fundamental principle of Nature, and present additional evidence which supports this.

Keywords: Unification; chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR); storage of negentropy; origins of order; complexity; life is fundamental principle of Nature.

I. INTRODUCTION

Niels Bohr once said that physicists should study philosophy. Einstein once said (to Heisenberg) "It is theory which decides what we can observe".[1] There is a problem in physics: theoreticians don't do experiments, but study mathematics, whilst experimentalists, who study Nature, don't

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do theoretical physics, in the main. The net result is that experimentalists are being told what to think by theoreticians who are disconnected from Nature. The solution to this problem, the author (an experimentalist) realised several decades ago, is to use philosophy to inspire experiments, and then work backwards to the correct theory. In a sense this returns to the old days of natural philosophy, before physics became a profession. Please note, most of the philosophy has been replaced by mathematical theory or experimental results, details of which are given in the five papers cited below.

A. Philosophy and Experiment

The search to unify quantum mechanics and general relativity has led to a number of potential unified theories, or "Theories of Everything". But what is everything? Presumably it has the standard model embedded within it, but what about thermodynamics, or for that matter life? If thermodynamics is included, does that mean life is also included?

Life is normally excluded from physics, but it cannot be completely excluded because it has to be there in the brain of the physicist, because without life a physicist's brain does not compute. However, the starting point for this work was not philosophy, but experimental evidence presented at CERN that science is incorrect about life.

Basically living organisms are far too complex to have evolved by random chance within the known age of the Universe. Details of these calculations and references are given in the biophysics paper cited below. Furthermore, DNA contains significant numbers of large palindromes (i.e. sequences which read the same forwards and backwards such as 'Able was I ere I saw Elba' but double stranded), which are clearly not random. Thus calculations predict that DNA is not random in origin, and significant numbers of large palindromes provide experimental evidence that it is not random in practice. *This combination of calculation and experimental evidence is a physics-grade fact, not always found in biology, which shows that living organisms are not random in origin. Therefore there has to be source(s) of order.*

This triggered a long search for sources of order in physics and biology, the results of which are summarised in the following five papers. The reader is referred to these original papers for details and references. Please note, we did not set out to catalogue the blockages preventing unification. Instead they appeared as we researched the origins of order. For example the shortcomings of general relativity are discussed in the next subsection on the first paper.

The purpose of this paper is to present a higher level synthesis of these five papers. The

reader who comes from the point of view of the second law of thermodynamics, that there are no sources of order, needs to first consider sunlight shining on the earth's surface. Brittin and Gamow have shown that it enables negentropy to build up, provided it can be stored, for example by photosynthesis. However, photosynthesis is not physics. It would be more interesting if there is a *physical* mechanism(s) for the storage of negentropy, and this could help explain the origins of complexity before photosynthesis developed. We then did some simple experiments which suggested there may actually be a physical storage mechanism. In order to understand these provisional results and to do more detailed experiments, we needed a theoretical framework (for the storage of negative entropy). This is introduced in the phenomenology paper which comes first.

B. I: Evidence for Phenomena, including Magnetic Monopoles, Beyond 4-D Space-Time, and Theory Thereof.[2]

The reasoning in this phenomenology paper is, in the main, not from mathematical principles downwards, but from experimental results upwards to theory. As noted, Brittin and Gamow have used quantum theory to predict that sunlight lowers the entropy level at the earth's surface, when the negentropy is stored (eg by photosynthesis). We present experimental evidence for this effect in the second paper below,[3] which shows that reduced entropy levels persist in inanimate matter, contrary to the second law. This requires new physics to explain it, which we present in this first paper. We present only a summary here. The reader who wants details and references should consult the original paper cited above. (NB This separation of theory and experiment, required by reviewers, unfortunately prevents the results being presented sequentially.)

In order to develop the theory, we investigate another little known property of light, which makes it possible to detect magnetic monopoles. We present evidence, from the scientific literature, that magnetic monopoles have already been observed at low energies, but they are non-objective, possibly in another space-time, and have been ignored. Several experimentalists have shown that *magnetic monopoles only exist in the presence of intense illumination* and so do not seem to exist in their own right.

Mikhailov made repeated measurements and determined that the monopole charge is quantized as predicted by Dirac ($g = ng_D, n=1-5$); ($\bar{g} = (0.99 \pm 0.05)g_D$). These results are reproducible, and so should be considered physically real. We conclude that Dirac monopoles exist, however not in 4-D, but in another space-time.

In the second part of this paper, we introduce chronometric invariants to explain this. In

the 1930s, Landau and others realised general relativity is incomplete because it does not correct for the Observer's reference frame. When this is done for the general case, chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR) predicts a more complex structure to space-time (3,2), including a second time dimension which is directed from the future to the past in mirror space-time, and also new phenomena at low (eV) energies. More details of this theory and references are given in this paper.[2]

We bring together the above two theories to explain how light can switch (via the Brittin and Gamow effect) into another space-time predicted by chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR), to reveal phenomena there. Light lowers the entropy level and so reverses the arrow of time into the mirror world of CIGR, where time is directed from the future to the past, and *reveals* monopoles there. We call this the photo-mirror effect. This also explains the infinite length of the Dirac string. This reasoning is necessary to understand the experiments in the second, third and fourth papers.

C. II: Preliminary Evidence for a Second Time Dimension, and for Unification.[3]

Experiments are presented in this paper on the effects of visible light shining on water. The initial objective was to test Brittin and Gamow's theory that sunlight lowers the entropy level at the earth's surface. We detected this effect and found it persists for at least 10 months after exposure of water to sunlight (at least 17 days after halogen light), contrary to the second law of thermodynamics.

In order to investigate this further experimentally, we needed a theoretical framework. The photo-mirror hypothesis (see the previous paper) is that light can switch the arrow of time into that of the mirror world of CIGR, via the Brittin and Gamow effect. Experimental evidence is presented that when visible photons interact with water, they switch small (0.2 to 1.5 microns) "quantized" regions of water into the mirror world state; and their brightness distributions match the energy spectrum of the halogen light source ($\chi^2/DF = 1.49$ and 0.94 respectively) indicating causality. This is detailed evidence for the Brittin and Gamow effect.

Furthermore, these domains persist (for at least 20 and 27 days respectively), which is evidence for the second time dimension, and there is experimental evidence that they appear to be surrounded by the membrane also predicted by CIGR (so they have an "inside" and an "outside"). Together these are evidence for CIGR and for the photo-mirror effect, which links quantum mechanics and general relativity, and so *this is preliminary experimental evidence for unification.*

Please note. Evidence for direct transmission of a signal from the future to the past is presented below.

As a result of the photo-mirror effect, water can store the negentropy produced when photons interact with it. Thus quantum mechanics and CIGR provide a memory for processes which reduce entropy levels. We make the hypothesis that water can be used to detect possible new type(s) of radiation, other than photons, which lower entropy levels, if they exist. We present evidence for this in the next paper.

D. III: Preliminary Evidence for a New Type of Radiation in Sunlight.[4]

In view of the evidence for the photo-mirror effect and unification above, we reason that mirror space-time in CIGR could form the basis for the hidden sector of a new unified theory. In the absence of a properly formulated theory, we make the hypothesis that there may be other phenomena in the mirror sector, which lower entropy levels.

We search for such new phenomena using water as the detector, together with two techniques adapted from the previous paper, which provide evidence for a new type of radiation (not electromagnetic, but in mirror space-time) in sunlight. Firstly, a special microscope technique is used to show that there is a component of sunlight which creates 12 micron structures in water which are square/pyramidal in shape, and hence lowers the entropy level. These structures persist for at least 3 weeks, contrary to the second law of thermodynamics. Secondly, we use a modified viscosity technique to search for this new type of radiation in sunlight, if any, which penetrates 12 micron aluminium foil and lowers the entropy level of water. Off-line we measured viscosity to detect changes in entropy more precisely. Evidence is presented for a new type of radiation in sunlight, which penetrates the Al foil and increases the viscosity of water, hence lowers its entropy level, and this effect persists.

We repeated this experiment and find it is reproducible. The reduced entropy levels persist in both experiments for at least for 5 to 17 weeks after exposure respectively. The effect is 10.1 times the systematic errors, and 5.6 and 10.2 σ greater than the controls (incandescent light and non-irradiated) respectively. Neither WISPs nor light-shining-through-wall (LSW) effects can explain these results. This new type of radiation in sunlight appears to be in the second sector of the above hypothetical new unified theory.

E. IV: Preliminary Evidence for (Mirror) Quarks, Preons and possibly Dark Matter.[5]

In this paper, we investigate the nature of matter in mirror space-time. Chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR) predicts that massive particles are 4-D dipoles, with the positive mass state being in normal 4D space time, and the negative mass state being in mirror space-time, where time is directed from the future to the past. However CIGR has not yet been unified with quantum mechanics, and so this result may change.

We investigate Ehrenhaft's (and other's) claims to have observed fractional electric charges, *taking into account this new physics*. We then examine the results of the experiments by Millikan to determine the charge on the electron, *also from the point of view of this new physics*. We conclude that Ehrenhaft and others did observe fractional charges, and that Millikan also observed a few of these (*not in normal space-time but in mirror space-time*), thereby providing some corroboration. We explain the differences in their results in terms of different objectives, different hardware, and the photo-mirror effect.

We present preliminary evidence that fractional charges (i.e. mirror quarks and preons) have been revealed in mirror space-time, by reversing the direction of time via the photo-mirror effect. The data rule out preon models with charges of $e/3$ and $2e/3$, but are compatible with preons with charges of $e/9$. Better data and a more complete theory would be desirable. We make the conjectures that preons could be dark matter, and that the mirror sector eliminates the need for inflation.

F. V: Biophysics: Astrobiology and Possible Origins of the Complexity of Life.[6]

It is a premise of astrobiology that life exists elsewhere in the Universe. In which case there would need to be mechanisms for complex states to develop out of inanimate matter, either in an orderly or random ways. So we investigate biological phenomena for evidence for order and/or randomness. We start by considering the geometries of life (eg logarithmic spirals; fractals) and the symmetries of living organisms. These suggest that life is not random, but orderly.

However it has long been an assumption of biology that living organisms have evolved by random mutations and natural selection. We present in more detail the theoretical calculations mentioned above, with references, which show that simple proteins, and even a simple cell, could not have evolved by random processes within the known age of the Universe. Furthermore we also present the experimental evidence for palindromes in DNA, for which there is considerable evidence, including

numerous large ones. We conclude that *DNA did not evolve by random mutations*. This suggests that either life on earth is some kind of statistical fluke, and is rare or non-existent elsewhere. Or there are source(s) of order in Nature, in which case life could have developed in other parts of the Universe as well.

We consider briefly a number of theories of life, including those based upon self-organisation and systems theory, various biological approaches and physics. We did not find any satisfactory explanations for the origin of order. (NB Systems and complexity theorists argue that complexity emerges spontaneously by self-organisation. Specifically there is evidence for self assembly. However, if there are unknown (hidden) mechanisms (as presented in the above physics papers) for the creation of order out of chaos, then it would then be neither spontaneous, nor self-organising. So such theories are purely speculative.)

We note Szent-Györgyi's criticisms of molecular biology, that as one descends from higher levels to lower (via organs, cells, molecules) one is left empty-handed because proteins outside cells are lifeless. We present evidence that water is essential for life, but heavy water is poisonous, which suggests that life is *physical*. However, none of these theories supply the order required.

We present a preliminary physics theory of the food chain, which shows that sunlight creates order on the earth's surface, which can be stored by photosynthesis. But what happened before photosynthesis developed? Either chlorophyll developed by random chemical processes, OR there is some physical mechanism for storing the order produced by sunlight, which enables more complex states to build up from inanimate matter.[7] We conclude that if such a storage mechanism exists then life is physical, if not then it is chemical in origin. Simple laboratory experiments may detect this storage mechanism and show that life is not random but physical, and so likely to exist elsewhere in the Universe. In fact there is evidence for this memory in the physics papers summarised above, which suggests life is physical. We consider this in more detail below.

II. EVIDENCE FOR THE SECOND (HIDDEN) SECTOR AND FOR UNIFICATION

Many unified theories predict a second (often hidden) sector. However, we don't yet have a theory, and in fact we are working backwards from experiment towards a possible theory. So let us review the evidence for a possible second sector. However, making sense of our experiments was difficult without some theoretical inputs, so we adopted CIGR.

The origins of CIGR are that general relativity is incomplete because it does not correct for the reference frame of the Observer, hence the need for CIGR which does. This seems perfectly

logical and even compelling. CIGR predicts a more complex structure for space-time, with a second time dimension directed from the future to the past, in mirror space-time.[2] We have obtained experimental evidence for this second time dimension, and for the membrane which separates mirror space-time from normal space-time.[3] So on the basis of this theoretical and experimental evidence, we accept CIGR.

We also made the hypothesis that mirror space-time is the basis for the second sector of a new unified theory. If mirror space-time is the spacial basis for this hidden sector, then just as there are forces and different states of matter in normal space-time, we would expect (for symmetry reasons) new force(s) and different states of matter to be found in mirror space time, if it is part of the hidden sector of the unified theory.

In the third paper, we find evidence for a new type of radiation in sunlight, which passes through a 12 micron aluminium foil and produces ordered patterns in water which persist. We show in considerable detail in this paper, that this radiation is not known to science and that it is in the mirror sector.[4] The 12 micron square/pyramidal structures it produces in water, persist. This suggests that it is a previously unknown force in the mirror sector.

Furthermore, in the first paper we combined the Brittin and Gamow effect with CIGR to show that photons could switch the direction of time into that of mirror time, by lowering the entropy level of the system, and called this the photo-mirror hypothesis.[2] We used this, together with the prediction from CIGR that massive particles are dipoles with the negative mass state being in mirror space time, to explain the observation of magnetic monopoles under intense illumination in the mirror sector. (NB An attractive force between monopoles would cause pairs of negative mass states to repel each other, so that magnetic dipoles would not form, even at low energies.)

In the second paper we found experimental evidence for the photo-mirror effect, which justifies its usage to explain the observation of magnetic monopoles.[3] Furthermore, the photo-mirror effect depends upon both quantum mechanics (Brittin and Gamow) and mirror space-time (CIGR), so *this is preliminary evidence for the unification of the two.*

In the 4th paper, we investigate the evidence for fractional electric charges, in the light of this new physics. Firstly the mirror sector makes it possible for there to be a second system of quantisation of charge, with the atomic system being in normal space-time and the second system (e.g. mirror-quarks and preons) being in mirror space-time. Secondly the level of illumination could determine which sector one was observing because of the photo-mirror effect.

Whilst the evidence is not as good as Mikhailov's measurements of magnetic monopoles, nevertheless there is evidence for fractional charges in mirror space-time as small as $e/9$. and possibly

as small as $e/19$. Most of the observations of fractional charges were made by Europeans who had superior optical equipment and apparently used higher levels of illumination - see this reference for details.[5] Never-the-less there are a few fractional charge events in Millikan's data, which he tended to reject since he was so focused on proving the atomic hypothesis. Incidentally this data appears to be one of the first observations of preons. The data rule out preon models with charges of $e/3$ and $2e/3$, and support preon models with charges of $e/9$ or smaller.

To summarise, there is evidence for mirror space-time and its second time dimension, for a new type of radiation, possibly a new force, and for these new states of matter (magnetic monopoles, mirror-quarks and preons) in the mirror sector. Furthermore, there is evidence for the photo-mirror effect and hence for unification of QM and CIGR. Thus this is preliminary evidence for the second sector of a new unified theory based upon quantum mechanics and chronometric invariant general relativity CIGR.

A. The Nature of this New Unified Theory

The Universe of modern science appears to be a vast violent place, with black holes, quasars and its origins in the Big Bang. When the Observer is put into general relativity, the theory (CIGR) predicts small-scale, low energy, complex phenomena, and there is experimental evidence for these. This is a very different type of universe, and may explain why we have started to find evidence for the unification of QM with CIGR. Furthermore, the theory predicts that there is a mechanism for the storage of negentropy, provided by the second time dimension of CIGR. We have found several pieces of experimental evidence for this storage of negentropy.[3, 4]

Please note the mechanism for the storage of negentropy, does not depend upon upon any of the more peculiar aspects of quantum mechanics, such as entanglement or the measurement problem, but upon the mirror sector of CIGR with its second time dimension.[2-4]

In the biophysics paper above, we have concluded that *if* there is a physical mechanism(s) for the storage of negentropy produced by the Brittin and Gamow effect, *then life is physical in origin*, because then more complex states can build up and persist, before photosynthesis develops, or living organisms actually form.[6] We have presented detailed evidence for this storage in the second paper.[3] *Therefore life appears to be physical in origin, and thus a principle of Nature.*

B. The Living Universe Hypothesis

The current (unwritten) assumption of physics, is that *the Universe is a dead, lifeless, inert machine*, and so life is excluded from fundamental physics. However the role of local gauge invariance in the theories of electromagnetism,[8] and the other two forces in the standard model, suggests that *communication* is a principle of Nature. So is the Universe a dead, lifeless, *communicating* machine, or is it alive in some way? Furthermore, the brain of a physicist has to be alive, but is this a primary or secondary phenomenon? The problem is, the brain has a weakness: *it does not know what it does not know*. [9] Therefore we need to test this assumption. The problem is it is a negative assumption and so difficult to test. The normal procedure is to make the opposite hypothesis, and look for evidence for or against that.

In view of the above reasoning and evidence, we make the hypothesis that *life is a fundamental principle of nature*,. The picture which is developing is that there are two sectors, one based upon normal 4-D space-time which is extensively studied by physicists, and the other, based upon mirror space-time, for which there is some limited evidence (mostly misinterpreted).[2, 5] The mirror sector stores negentropy,[3, 4] *and so plays an active role in the creation of complexity*. [7] If living organisms are formed in this way, there should be some evidence for mirror-time occurring in them.

Libet and his colleagues have done experiments which provide some evidence for this. They used human subjects, and applied a stimulus to the back of the subject's hand. This stimulus was either flashes of light, or mild electrical pulses. If the duration of the stimulus was less than about 500 msec, then the subjects were unaware of it, even though their brains showed evidence for the stimulation. Thus there is a minimum duration of stimulus, below which it is ignored, which is perhaps not surprising. If the duration of the stimulus is longer than this minimum, then the subjects became aware of it. However, this conscious awareness does not occur after this minimum duration of 500 msec, *but when the stimulus started, 500 msec earlier*. They state:

There is an automatic subjective referral of the conscious experience backwards in time... The sensory experience would be "antedated" from the actual delayed time at which the neuronal state becomes adequate to elicit it; and the experience would appear subjectively to occur with no significant delay.[10]

So whilst it took 500 msec for the stimulus to be experienced subjectively, nevertheless *this awareness is shifted backwards in time to when the stimulus actually started*. In a previous paper

we have said that whilst we had evidence for time directed from the future to the past,[3] we had not sent a signal from the future to the past. The above experiment is preliminary evidence for such a signal.

If life is a fundamental principle of nature, then there may be non-biological life forms. For example viruses do not have a normal metabolism like bacteria, and so some scientists question whether they are alive. Thus the existence of viruses may support the hypothesis.

Furthermore, if life is a fundamental principle of nature, then the domains observed when photons interact with water,[3] could be the first step in the formation of cells, because they are low entropy states surrounded by a membrane. In which case creation of life could be a continuous process.

Crystals are currently thought to be lifeless. However they are highly ordered states of matter. Very briefly, many crystals can be recognised by their form and colour, just as plants can be so identified. Furthermore, crystals can be seeded and they grow. There is even evidence that some crystals (e.g. quartz) can regrow after being damaged. This subject deserves to be considered in more detail than we do here. Nevertheless it is possible that crystals are non-biological life forms.

C. Cosmology

The ideas of western physics go back to the Ancient Greeks. Pythagoras (580-500 BC) taught that the Cosmos is alive and there is hidden order, as shown by the number theory of music. In fact *Kosmos* means "the beautiful order of things".[11] Meanwhile Democritus (460-370 BC) was a leading proponent of the atomic theory, that everything is made from different arrangements of indivisible particles moving around in the "void". Not only has science shown that atoms are divisible, but chronometric invariants show that whilst there is a void, the particles of matter are not in it, but in normal or mirror space-time.

The phrase "Mirror Universe" has been used in a number of different dual theories of the universe. We refer to a couple here. The earliest comes from the idea that parity could be conserved if there was a parallel hidden (mirror) sector.[12] Another approach involves a "mid-point" (i.e. the big bang or Janus point) out of which two universes develop, with time in opposite directions, if that is possible.[13, 14] Barbour et. al. introduce the concept of *entaxy* from the Greek "towards order", as opposed to "entropy". Throughout our papers, we use the word "mirror" to refer to the hidden sector of CIGR with time directed from the future to the past, and related phenomenon (e.g. mirror matter).

We have made the conjectures that dark matter may consist of mirror matter (e.g. preons). Furthermore that mirror space-time may eliminate the need for inflation, with its problems of fine tuning - see appendices here.[5] In addition the absence of large amounts of antimatter, may be explained by the fact that mirror-matter has negative mass, and so is not antimatter (because the latter has positive inertial mass). Furthermore a Universe based upon CIGR is not going to easily run down to a “heat death”, nor have to have an unbelievably highly ordered initial state (which seems to contradict the Big Bang) but instead can be developing order (entaxy) from its beginning. It would be tempting to conclude that this confirms Pythagoras. However the Universe is dual and there is both order and disorder (entaxy and entropy), and so we conclude that Pythagoras was too optimistic.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND PREDICTIONS

We have presented an overview of the evidence for the unification of quantum mechanics and chronometric invariant general relativity (e.g. photo-mirror effect).[3] We have also presented evidence for phenomena in the second sector, based on mirror space-time (e.g. magnetic monopoles, mirror quarks, preons, a new type of radiation in sunlight).[2, 4, 5] In order to understand the complexity of living organisms, we have searched for sources of order, which has led us to unification. The reverse may apply, namely that unification leads to order.

We have presented evidence that life is physical in origin. In view of this evidence, we have made the hypothesis that *life is a fundamental principle of Nature*, and presented some additional evidence which supports this, contrary to the generally accepted negative assumption that the Universe is lifeless (see above). It is important to obtain additional evidence for or against this hypothesis, because physics should be based upon facts not assumptions.

If life is a fundamental principle of Nature, as the above evidence suggests, then life is likely to develop where starlight is shining on any potentially habitable planet. Given the large number of exo-planets found, extra-terrestrial life is likely to be quite widespread in the Universe. Therefore astrobiology is likely to succeed and find it.

Theoretical physicists interested in the quantisation of space-time, should note how it occurs when light interacts with water.[3] Those interested in developing the unified field theory, should seriously consider the experimental evidence we have presented for the unification of quantum mechanics and chronometric invariant general relativity. This already includes thermodynamics, and, given that CIGR includes the Observer, it is highly likely it will include life.

IV. LIMITATIONS

The evidence presented in this paper is part of an overview, and lacks detail. For the details and supporting references, the reader is referred to the five cited papers.[2–6] The author is not a cosmologist.

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